

Reviewing the European Union Emergency Trust Fund (EUTF for Africa): A Sustained Shift Towards Aid Securitisation

Cambridge Journal of Political Affairs
Volume 6, Issue 1 (2025): 12–29
© The Author(s) 2025
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16621096
cambridgepoliticalaffairs.co.uk

Lisa Lefebvre-Risso
University of Oxford

This article evaluates the European Union Emergency Trust Fund (EUTF) for Africa from 2015 to 2022 to determine if it constitutes a shift towards aid securitisation amid evolving migration and security priorities. It addresses the following research question: Has i) the rhetoric and ii) the substance of the EUTF for Africa shifted towards aid securitisation? This work is based on an in-depth analysis of EU primary sources, specifically a content analysis of the EUTF annual reports, board meeting minutes and other official reports published by the EU Commission. The work argues that both the rhetoric and substance of the EUTF have shifted towards aid securitisation, intensifying after 2017 with the adoption of new strategic objectives solely focused on migration management. Despite its initial aims of poverty alleviation and development, the EUTF has increasingly prioritised migration prevention and security initiatives.

INTRODUCTION

Across the OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) countries, development programmes have progressively shifted towards aid securitisation, prompting debates on a broader definition of Official Development Assistance (ODA) (Castillejo, 2016, p. 26). ODA, considered the gold standard in foreign assistance, is defined by the OECD (2023) as assistance aiming to promote “the economic development and welfare of developing countries.” Aid securitisation, as defined by Olivé and Pérez (2021, p.1903), is “a process where targets such as security and stability ... crowd out human and sustainable development goals.” Various scholars have warned about EU development policy potentially aligning with its migration and security agenda and shifting away from its traditional primary goal of poverty alleviation enshrined in the Treaty of Lisbon (Lauwers et al., 2021, p. 72; Castillejo, 2016, p. 23). Under EU treaties, development projects incorporating security and migration initiatives should remain rooted in development prerogatives (Castillejo, 2016, p. 23). The European Union Emergency Trust Fund (EUTF) for Africa, established amid the 2015 migration crisis, serves as the most prominent and explicit illustration of such a trend (Lauwers et al., 2021, p. 72). Its design and implementation pose questions as to its alignment with the EU and ODA definition of development policy, and its potential diversion of aid towards reducing migration flows (Zaun and Nantermoz, 2023, p. 2987). Given that the European Union (EU) and its Member States (MS) are the largest global providers of ODA, the implications of the EUTF offer insights into trends in the EU response to global migration and changes to development policy.

The EUTF literature emerged in the early years of the programme, between 2016 and 2017, with little addition since then. During this period, the literature underscored the ambiguous nature of the fund and raised concerns about a possible shift towards aid securitisation. The main concern was the fund’s characterisation as an emergency tool aimed at solving the root causes of irregular immigration. This revealed the inconsistency between short-term migration goals and long-term developmental objectives, which can hardly be solved by a five-year emergency fund (Youngs and Zihniglo, 2021, p. 132). The absence of a coherent long-term strategy to tackle developmental challenges, which have already received billions of dollars in assistance, underscores the ill-suited nature of the EUTF to achieve its intended impact (Castillejo, 2017, p. 2). While the allocated sum of five billion euros may appear substantial, when considering the breadth of the programme—aimed at addressing the root causes of migration, insecurity, and instability across twenty-six countries hosting a quarter of the global refugee population—the inadequacy of both time and resources has been pointed out by experts and members of civil society (Castillejo, 2016, p. 3). All twenty EU officials interviewed by Castillejo (2016, p. 4) admitted that the

chances of solving these issues through the EUTF alone were “pretty dim,” raising questions about its underlying objectives.

Much of the literature emerging in 2016 anticipated that the EUTF would subvert developmental objectives to prioritise issues on the EU security agenda, such as reducing migration flows (Fakhoury, 2016, p. 68). Fakhoury (2016, p. 68) argued that the programme exemplified a broader shift in EU development policy, prioritising security and migration issues over its traditional emphasis on value promotion and development. The debate around the launch of the fund extended beyond academia, with members of civil society such as Oxfam arguing its setup “within the context of the European migration agenda raised concerns that aid would be promoted to serve European interests”—primarily by curbing migration flows during the peak of the migration crisis (Oxfam, 2017, p. 2). The existing literature lacks a comprehensive assessment of the programme beyond 2016, aside from Pacciardi’s (2021, p. 4) review. The contracting period concluded in 2021, offering an opportunity to examine the entirety of the programme’s activities and narratives. While the literature investigates the fund’s initial shift towards aid securitisation, it remains focused on its funding of security initiatives rather than examining it alongside its rhetoric (Fakhoury, 2016; Castillejo, 2016; Castillejo, 2017). It is essential to update these findings in light of new evidence and analyse both the EUTF’s rhetoric and substance. This work thus fills this gap by providing a comprehensive and updated evaluation of the programme.

This article assesses whether the EUTF illustrates an enduring shift towards aid securitisation. Its ambiguous goals and rhetoric pose questions as to whether migration and security policies subverted development goals for the duration of the programme. It is particularly interesting to look at these issues from two angles: i) the EUTF rhetoric and ii) the substance of the programme. I will examine the EUTF’s evolution from 2015 to 2022 and address the following research question: Has i) the rhetoric and ii) the substance of the EUTF for Africa shifted towards aid securitisation?

To answer this question, this work will focus on an analysis of the EUTF at the macro-level narrative, mainly communicated by the European Commission. While other actors shape and take part in the implementation of the programme, the Commission plays a central role as a hegemonic actor (as outlined in Chapter 1) (Pacciardi, 2021, p.1). This article will first offer an overview of the literature and present the theoretical framework used to operationalise the concept of aid securitisation, based on Oliv and Prez’s (2021, p.1903) definition. I will then justify the methodology and primary sources used. The first chapter delves into the internal dynamics shaping the EUTF rhetoric, examining diverging interests between the different EU agencies involved and the EU Member States within board meeting discussions from 2015 to 2022. The second chapter analyses the EUTF rhetoric through a content analysis of board meeting minutes and annual reports from 2015 to 2022, to better grasp the themes dominating both the internal and official discourse. These first chapters analyse whether the EUTF rhetoric has shifted towards aid securitisation. Finally, the last chapter focuses on the substance of the programme, looking at its official and underlying objectives, funding allocated to each strategic objective, and its impact on future EU development programmes.

Through this analysis, the article finds that both the EUTF’s rhetoric and substance have shifted towards aid securitisation, and more intensely so since 2017 with a shift in strategic objectives. Indeed, the EUTF’s initial goals of poverty alleviation and fostering development have been subverted by migration prevention and security initiatives (Langan and Price, 2021, p. 506).

Literature Review

The existing literature on the EUTF, mainly emerging during its initial stages in 2016, lies at the crossroads of various scholarly fields: the securitisation of migration issues, the migration-development nexus, and broader discussions surrounding EU development policy. I will subsequently provide some background information on the EUTF.

Indeed, the foreign aid literature has long established a consensus that aid is not solely geared towards meeting the developmental needs of recipient countries but is predominantly aligned with donors’ interests (Hoeffler and Outram, 2011, p. 237). Foreign aid thus serves to advance the donor’s—in this case, mainly EU Member States’—concerns, and more recently, extend their security policy objectives (Youngs and Zihnioglu, 2021, p. 126). In its 2016 Global Strategy on Foreign and Security Policy, the EU explicitly acknowledged a shift towards a development policy more closely aligned with its strategic priorities (EU

Commission, 2016, p. 11). This poses questions about whether the EUTF's development objectives are being sidelined.

Securitisation of Migration Issues

The securitisation of EU migration policies gained momentum following the Arab Spring, which led to a surge in migration to the EU (Fakhoury, 2016, p. 68). The 2015 migration crisis, where more than 1.3 million refugees and migrants arrived in Europe in a single year, marked a pivotal moment after which the EU fully incorporated security concerns into its approach to migration (UNHCR, 2016). Conceptualised by the Copenhagen School, the securitisation theory delineates the process by which actors frame a certain issue as a significant security threat (Fakhoury, 2016, p. 69). This framing is internalised by the public through public officials' speeches, ultimately justifying the adoption of unprecedented measures and spending to resolve the crisis (Fakhoury, 2016, p. 69). Despite some Member States initially, such as Germany, advocating for welcoming policies, uncontrolled and illegal migration has increasingly been constructed and accepted as a threat to the EU's security (Lavenex and Kunz, 2008, p. 440). The growing body of literature on aid securitisation and the securitisation of migration flows outlines the EUTF's role in promoting remote governance and responding to this domestic political crisis through aid (Fakhoury, 2016, pp. 69-70). The literature has sparked a revival of the migration-development nexus, instrumentalising aid to deter migration flows and respond to politically salient issues.

The Migration-Development Nexus

Since the early 2000s, donors have promoted migration and development policies jointly, under the framework of the migration-development nexus (Lavenex and Kunz, 2008, p. 440). This concept suggests that as levels of development and stability increase, migration flows will decrease (Clemens and Postel, 2018, p. 667). Western aid agencies and politicians perceive migration and development as interconnected issues, resulting in decades of aid policies aimed at deterring migration (Clemens and Postel, 2018, p. 667). In the case of the EUTF, this development-led approach to migration is closely linked to the security-development nexus, wherein security is regarded as a prerequisite for development. Aid is thus directed towards security and stability initiatives, such as funding law enforcement agencies (Olivíe and Pérez, 2019, p. 182). Lying at the intersection of these concepts, the EUTF contends that addressing instability in conflict-ridden states through development will, in turn, reduce immigration to the EU, despite academic research suggesting that economic growth leads to more migration as emigrating becomes accessible to a wider part of the population (Olivíe and Pérez, 2019, p. 182; Castillejo, 2016, p. 5). Although this approach is not new, as outlined in the 2003 European Security Strategy, the EUTF is unique in its operationalisation of this approach, being the most ambitious EU instrument of its kind (Council of the EU, 2003, p. 2).

EU Development Policy

Most of the research on the EUTF occurred in 2016, with some scholars positing from the outset that the fund was inclining towards a shift in the primary objective of EU foreign aid. Clemens and Postel (2018, p. 667) contend that during its early years, the EUTF prioritised deterring migration over fostering development and economic prosperity. Indeed, some suggested the EUTF utilised aid strategically to exert pressure on partner countries, such as Nigeria and Sudan, to cooperate on issues such as readmission and return policies, many of which were unfavourable to them before the introduction of the fund (Youngs and Zihniglo, 2021, p. 130). Returns and readmission policies involve the voluntary or forced repatriation of irregular migrants to their country of origin, subject to the agreement of the respective third country (European Council directive 2001/40/EC, 2001). Moreover, the European Parliament raised concerns that the use of the EDF to fund the EUTF might divert development funds away from countries with the greatest need for aid that are not included in the EUTF, towards countries that are the most relevant for the EU migratory agenda, either as countries of origin or along migratory routes (Castillejo, 2016, p. 24; European Parliament, 2016, p. 5). Rather than using traditional metrics to allocate aid, such as GDP per capita or human development index, the EU seemed to prioritise its strategic interests, potentially violating Article 208 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (Castillejo, 2016, p. 24). This suggested a departure from the EU's initial commitments in development policy, such as human rights, democracy promotion, and values-based partnerships promoting best practices (Castillejo, 2017, p. 3). Claims that the EUTF constitutes a shift towards aid securitisation remain unanswered, as scholars focused on its first two years of running and failed to examine the entirety of the programme. The literature requires updating by analysing whether the EUTF subverts development for other aims, by examining both its rhetoric and substance.

Background To the Case Study

The European Union Emergency Trust Fund for stability and addressing the root causes of irregular migration and forced displacement (EUTF) was created in November 2015 following the Valletta Summit on Migration (EU Commission, 2016, p. 4). It covers 26 countries and is divided into three regional windows: Sahel and Lake Chad (SLC), the Horn of Africa (HOA) and North of Africa (NOA). The EUTF rests on the assumption that migration flows are driven by instability and underdevelopment in these regions and aims to address its root causes to reduce irregular migration to the EU. In 2015, 1.5 billion euros were initially pledged to the EUTF, to reach a total of almost 5 billion euros in 2021 and the adoption of 248 projects. While 25 Member States and other donors (Norway and Switzerland) contributed, a majority of the funds came from the European Development Fund (EDF) (European Commission, 2020, p. 1; EUTF, 2023). The EUTF's contracting period ended in December 2021, with projects continuing to be monitored until 2025.

The EUTF is governed by two main bodies, chaired by the European Commission: The Strategic Board, in charge of the global strategy, and the three regional Operational Committees, in charge of selecting projects. These bodies include contributing EU Member States and donors with voting rights based on a 3-million-euro contribution threshold, while recipient countries might sit on the board as observers (European Commission, 2020). Its broad scope is outlined in the four strategic objectives (SO) examined in Chapter 3.

The EUTF's formation in late 2015 acted as a response to the highly politicised migration crisis, which peaked in 2015 following conflicts in Libya and Syria (Castillejo, 2017, p. 2). The surge in migration, coupled with intense media coverage, placed immense pressure on EU Member States and was framed as a political crisis, exacerbated by the proliferation of anti-migration discourse (Kiratli, 2021, p. 53). The rapid launch of the EUTF marks an attempt by the EU to politically respond to this crisis by solving the root causes of irregular migration (Kiratli, 2021, p. 53; Zaun and Nantermoz, 2023, p. 2986).

As such, the EUTF is without doubt tailored for the EU domestic audience. While citizens will not normally be aware of and concerned about the EUTF, it is mainly addressed to experts and members of civil society, such as Oxfam, that initially raised concerns about the diversion of EU development aid. The programme places a strong emphasis on the visibility of its activities, exemplified by the creation of its own website and social media platforms (EU Commission, 2016, p. 5). The EUTF website offers a plethora of information, including the EUTF Annual Reports and a 'News and Stories' section highlighting some key successes (EUTF, n.d.). Efforts have been made to enhance the programme's accessibility to a wider audience; notably, the format of the Annual Reports was transformed after 2018, becoming more concise and user-friendly, going from 130 pages to under 70 pages, with a more accessible design (EU Commission, 2018). The material found on the website, particularly the Annual reports, should thus be analysed as tailored for a domestic audience and mirroring the EUTF's official rhetoric.

The literature, emerging in 2016 and 2017, anticipates that the EUTF will constitute a shift towards aid securitisation but lacks a comprehensive overview of the duration of the programme. This article fills this gap by answering the following research question: Has i) the rhetoric and ii) substance of the European Union Emergency Trust Fund for Africa (EUTF) shifted towards aid securitisation?

Theoretical Framework

This article aims to assess whether the EUTF shifted towards aid securitisation, aligning more with the EU's strategic interests and deviating from its stated developmental goal. If security and stability are given greater attention by the EUTF than development goals, this would constitute a case of aid securitisation (Olivíe and Pérez, 2021, p. 1903). Olivíe and Pérez (2021, p. 1905) provide a comprehensive framework to account for cases of EU aid securitisation, which I apply to the EUTF.

They first emphasise the role of elites in issuing aid securitisation through official reports; this article will examine the role of different directorates within the EU Commission and EU Member States. Aid securitisation rhetoric also emphasises that the donors' society should become safer because of the programme. Indeed, the EUTF seeks to respond to the 2015 migration crisis and the security threat it poses to the EU. Moreover, the aid discourse aims to convince its audience through the EUTF website and annual reports; in this case, the audience would be the EU experts and academics who raised concerns about a shift towards aid securitisation (as mentioned in the background section). Nyman argues elites, here EU Member States and Commissioners, securitise aid to give the programme "extra priority, leading

to an increased public profile and/or budget;” this is exemplified by the exceptional resources the EUTF was granted, due to its framing as a response to migration as a security threat (Olivié and Pérez, 2021, p. 1905). Finally, aid securitisation operates within a specific context wherein the rise of populist anti-migration nationalist discourse in several EU Member States led aid to be perceived as a solution to domestic concerns, such as curbing migration inflows. According to Olivié and Pérez, these five conditions result in the securitisation of migration issues.

This article will thus examine whether the rhetoric and substance of the EUTF shifted towards aid securitisation, drawing from Olivié and Pérez’s framework. Chapter 1 will specifically focus on elites, their internal rhetoric, and divisions. By looking at the different discourses of the EUTF and its internal dynamics, Chapter 2 will expand on the fund’s audience and the effects on the donor’s civil society. Finally, Chapter 3 will look at whether the substance of the EUTF has shifted towards aid securitisation, examining the different strategic objectives and projects funded by the EUTF, and whether they constitute a case of aid securitisation. This comprehensive analysis will provide strong evidence of whether the EUTF’s i) rhetoric and ii) substance have shifted towards aid securitisation.

Methodology

This article uses a mixed-method approach, evaluating primary data found in EU official reports and meetings, data based on the EUTF fundings and projects, and a qualitative evaluation of the literature around aid securitisation and EU development policy from 2015 to 2022. The EUTF website offers a wealth of publicly accessible reports and documents, including annual reports, case studies, and midterm evaluations (EUTF, n.d.). This research primarily rests on an in-depth analysis of the EUTF annual reports from 2016 to 2022 and the board meeting minutes from 2015 to 2022, accompanied by other documents issued by EU official bodies, as illustrated in Table 1. While development policy is a shared competence between the EU member states and the Commission, this article will focus on the EUTF’s governance by the EU Commission and its relevant directorates (Furness and Gänzle, 2017, p. 480). By scrutinising and evaluating the EU’s reports and discourse while juxtaposing them with critical scholarly sources, I evaluate the evolution of the EUTF and seek to uncover the degree to which its rhetoric and substance have shifted towards aid securitisation from 2015 to 2022.

Board meeting minutes	Annual reports	Other EU official reports
Board meeting minutes 2015	EUTF Annual report 2016	European Commission (no date) <i>Emergency Trust Fund for Africa</i> website
Board meeting minutes 2016	EUTF Annual report 2017	European Commission (2020) ‘Mid-term Evaluation of the European Union Emergency Trust Fund for stability and addressing root causes of irregular migration and displaced persons in Africa 2015-2019’
Board meeting minutes 2017	EUTF Annual report 2018	European Commission (2021) ‘Learning Lessons from the EUTF – Phase 2 - Paving the way for future programming on migration, mobility and forced displacement’
Board meeting minutes 2018	EUTF Annual report 2019	European Court of Auditors (2018) ‘European Union Emergency Trust Fund for Africa: Flexible but lacking focus’
Compte Rendu de la Cinquième Réunion du FFUE 2018	Rapport Annuel du FFUE 2020	
Board meeting minutes 2019	EUTF Annual report 2021	
Board meeting minutes 2020	EUTF Annual report 2022	
Board meeting minutes 2021		
Board meeting minutes 2022		

Table 1. List of primary sources analysed.

I conducted a content analysis of the EUTF annual reports from 2016 to 2022 and the board meeting minutes from 2015 to 2022, hand-coding for six thematic clusters: migration, development, security, humanitarian-development nexus, humanitarian-development-peace nexus, and conflict, which is a standard method used in the EU development policy literature (Olivié and Pérez, 2019, p. 183). Using hand-coding allowed me to accurately capture the meanings of the words relevant to this analysis. For instance, ‘development’ could also refer to the creation of a strategy, but this interpretation was not reflected in the code. The entirety of the annual reports was coded, excluding the financial reports, annexes, and case study boxes, resulting in 278 pages included in the content analysis. The entirety of the board meeting minutes was coded, resulting in 51 pages included in the content analysis. Using the same thematic clusters for both documents enables a robust comparison of their rhetoric and confidence in the results. Table 2 presents the different words coded under each thematic cluster. The board meeting minutes for the fifth board meeting and the 2020 annual reports were only available in French and were thus translated by the author.

Name of the thematic cluster	Migration	Development	Security	Conflict	Humanitarian-development nexus	Humanitarian-development-peace nexus
Words included in the code	Migration/ Migrants/ Migrant / Migration management / Migrate / Migratory flow	Development / Aid / Foreign aid / Developmental / DEVCO	Security / Insecurity / Securitisatio	Conflict / Armed conflict / Conflict prevention	Humanitarian- development nexus	Humanitarian- development- peace nexus
Words included in the French code	Migration / Migrants / Migrant / Gestion migratoire / Flux migratoires	Développement / Aide / Aide internationale / Développement / DEVCO	Sécurité / Insécurité / Securitisatio	Conflit / Conflit armé / Prévention des conflits	Lien entre l'aide humanitaire et le développement	Lien entre l'aide humanitaire, le développement et la paix

Table 2. Thematic clusters coded.

Although analysing the minutes from the board meetings provides valuable insights into the internal discussions and divisions among different members of the strategic board, they are inherently limited by formal bargaining and diplomatic protocols. Nonetheless, they remain the only publicly available source offering insights into the diverse agendas of the actors involved. While these interventions may not fully reflect the DG's and states' intrinsic interests, time constraints and the confidential nature of private discussions made it impossible to gather more comprehensive insights through interviews or news reports.

CHAPTER 1: THE INTERNAL DYNAMICS SHAPING THE EUTF RHETORIC: REVIEWING THE STRATEGIC BOARD

This chapter aims to uncover the internal dynamics shaping the EUTF's rhetoric and strategic direction through an analysis of the board meeting minutes from 2015 to 2022. Firstly, this chapter explores the internal dynamic between the various EU agencies contributing to the EUTF, each with its different aspirations. The attempt to reconcile these diverging actors' interests creates ambiguity in the EUTF's goals and results. This chapter delves into the EU Member States' diverse agendas that they seek to advance through the EUTF.

A. Internal Dynamics Within the Eu Commission

While the EUTF board meetings involve both the EU's partner countries and external donors such as Switzerland, the former are relegated to observer status in board meetings, lacking influence over the EUTF's trajectory. Similarly, external donors wield little sway in shaping the rhetoric and discussions within the EUTF. Despite the EU emphasising the importance of local ownership and dialogue, the prominence of the Commission and its various directorates in setting the agenda and strategic orientation of the EUTF is evident in the structure of the board meetings. Chaired consistently by the Directorate-General for International Cooperation and Development (DG DEVCO), renamed Directorate-General for

International Partnerships (DG INTPA) in 2021, EU directorates first present their findings in their respective areas of expertise. Only after these presentations are completed are comments from all participants entertained. The Chair then closes the meeting, addressing concerns raised and pledging to incorporate comments “to the extent possible” into the trajectory of the EUTF (EU Commission, 2015, p. 4).

Five main EU agencies are present in the board meetings, each contributing expertise in their respective domains. The European External Action Service (EEAS) supervises the EU’s external relations with partner countries (Keukeleire and Raube, 2013, p. 566). Meanwhile, the Directorate-General for Neighbourhood and Enlargement Negotiations (DG NEAR) is responsible for the governance and implementation of the North of Africa window, leveraging its existing presence in the region through the European Neighbourhood Policy (ENP). Although not directly involved in implementing specific windows, the Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs (DG HOME) participates in board meetings to monitor migration trends and policies. Similarly, the Directorate-General for European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations (DG ECHO) contributes its expertise in conflict zones and humanitarian aid. Lastly, DG DEVCO/INTPA manages the HOA and SLC windows and holds a central place in the EUTF governance. Each of these five agencies advocates for distinct agendas within the EUTF, reflecting their varied core missions and priorities.

A close inspection of the minutes reveals that DG DEVCO/INTPA, despite presiding over board meetings, failed to preserve a balance between developmental concerns and migration issues, allowing other DGs to steer discussions toward migration matters (Castillejo, 2016, p. 7). DG NEAR played a prominent role in this shift, consistently highlighting the challenges posed by increased migration flows from the NOA window, particularly emphasising concerns regarding Libya, the main departure point for migrants bound for Italy and Malta (EU Commission, 2017, p. 1). DG NEAR advocated for increased funding for the region and prioritised projects aimed at building capacity for border management (EU Commission, 2017, p. 1). When evaluating the results of the EUTF, DG NEAR focused on its impact on migratory flows, despite the absence of a proven causal link between decreasing migration flows and the EUTF’s activities (EU Commission, 2018, p. 1). The DG HOME echoed this narrative and emphasised the need to direct EUTF funding towards initiatives deterring irregular migration to the EU and prioritising returns and reintegration (EU Commission, 2017, p. 1). The EEAS also shifted its attention to pillars 2-5 of the Valletta Action Plan (VAP), aimed at decreasing migration flows, arguing that pillar 1, which focuses on the development aspects of migration, should be funded by other instruments (EU Commission, 2017, p. 4). As such, these three main agencies consistently prioritised migration issues in board meetings, steering discussions towards increasing funding, and redirecting the EUTF towards addressing migration-related issues rather than its initial objective of poverty alleviation.

Among the five agencies involved, only DG ECHO actively advocated for increased attention towards development, emphasising its link with humanitarian assistance. Indeed, DG ECHO consistently stressed the importance of addressing the causes of migration and forced displacement as the core mission of the EUTF (EU Commission, 2018, p. 2). The agency underscored the pivotal role the EUTF could play in linking development and humanitarian aid, through the humanitarian-development nexus, followed by the humanitarian-development-peace nexus since 2020 (EU Commission, 2018, p. 2). These nexuses emerged in 2015 in the UN sustainable development goals, emphasising the need to build resilience and stability through linking humanitarian aid and development cooperation, specifically targeting vulnerable populations (EU Commission, 2020, p. 18). DG ECHO participated in the implementation of pilot projects within the HOA and SLC windows (EU Commission, 2019, p. 2). While DG ECHO succeeded in episodically adding these nexuses to the agenda, as will be outlined in Chapter 2, short-term migration management goals prevailed and subverted developmental objectives (Youngs and Zihnioglu, 2021, p. 130).

B- Diverging Interests of EU Member States

Another key finding from analysing the minutes was that the 25 EU Member States involved each hold diverging priorities and interests, which have shaped the EUTF’s rhetoric and trajectory.

Similar to the varying stances of different EU agencies, the primary point of contention between the different Member States lies in the ambiguous objective of the EUTF: addressing the root causes of irregular immigration and forced displacement through a five-year emergency instrument (Castillejo, 2016, p.5). While some states emphasised the need for the EUTF to commit to its initial purpose and focus on addressing long-term developmental issues, others rather focused on pushing their migration

reduction agendas (EU Commission, 2016, p. 2). On the one hand, some states with established traditions in foreign aid programmes, such as the UK and Finland, advocated for “not losing focus on long-term development opportunities” (EU Commission, 2016, p. 2; Zaun and Nantermoz, 2023, p. 2995). Less affected by migration inflows due to their geography, these states prioritised long-term goals rather than using the EUTF to respond to the migration crisis. On the other hand, countries geographically closer to immigrants’ arrival points such as Italy and Malta, along with major destination countries such as France and Germany, see the EUTF as a means to enhance cooperation on migration issues and address immediate challenges to curb migration flows (EU Commission, 2016, p. 2; EU Commission, 2017, p. 2). For instance, Italy explicitly expressed concerns about the increase in immigrant arrivals from Libya and advocated for a collective response from the EU through the EUTF (EU Commission, 2018, pp. 3-5). Their argument is centred on the belief that the EUTF, as a short-term instrument, is ill-suited to address the root causes of development issues and should rather ‘focus its efforts to stop the flow of illegal migrants’ (EU Commission, 2016, p. 2). Indeed, Castillejo (2016, p. 26) conducted interviews of Member States officials, who advocated for the need to adapt to individual EU states’ political contexts, including demands from the public and parliaments to include migration issues in their development policy. From 2017, amid scarce resources and the significant financial contributions of some Member States advocating for stronger migration management, the programme shifted its focus towards addressing migration issues, as reflected in its six new priorities outlined in Chapter 3 (EU Commission, 2018, p. 5). The EUTF was redirected to address the immediate challenges posed by the rise in migration flows, while addressing the root causes of migration was deferred to other EU instruments.

This chapter demonstrates that the EUTF aimed to attract support for both long-term developmental goals and short-term migration management to reconcile diverging agendas within the EU Commission and its directorates and the EU Member States. In its initial years, the fund in part reconciled both goals, but from 2017, amidst constrained funding, the migration agenda subverted its objective of poverty alleviation, and its strategic orientation shifted towards aid securitisation.

CHAPTER 2: THE EUTF RHETORIC: ANALYSING ANNUAL REPORTS AND BOARD MEETINGS MINUTES

To gain a comprehensive understanding of the EUTF rhetoric, it is essential to analyse both the internal deliberations among stakeholders during the board meetings and the programme’s official discourse presented in the annual reports. This chapter aims to analyse whether the EUTF rhetoric has shifted towards aid securitisation, in both the programme’s internal dynamics and its resultant official discourse. As described by the EU Commission, the EUTF lies at the intersection of migration, development, and securitisation (EU Commission, 2020, p. 11). It is thus imperative to examine whether these concerns received equitable attention within the programme’s rhetoric. To gauge whether the EUTF’s rhetoric shifted towards aid securitisation, I coded the frequency of mentions of each thematic cluster to uncover the central themes in stakeholders’ discussions, thereby illuminating the EUTF’s underlying aims. This chapter will first delve into the EUTF internal rhetoric by examining board meeting minutes held between 2015 and 2022. It will then compare this against the content of the EUTF annual reports spanning from 2016 to 2022.

A- Board Meetings Minutes

Firstly, the board meeting minutes provide valuable insights into the internal discourse of the EUTF, shedding light on the strategic priorities of different actors and what they aim to achieve with the programme. Each board meeting was presided over by the acting Director General of DG DEVCO, which was renamed DG INTPA in 2021. This grants DG DEVCO/INTPA a prominent role, in theory enabling it to advocate for enhancing the developmental aspect of the programme. Despite DG DEVCO/INTPA’s prominence in presiding over the board meetings, the EUTF failed to focus on one of its objectives: fostering development in the three regional windows of the programme.

Table 3. presents the results of the content analysis. Of the 51 pages analysed, migration-related terms were mentioned 219 times, compared to 53 mentions for development-related and 6 for security-related terms. References to security only revolved around border control and migration management, neglecting broader security considerations. This stark contrast underscores the dominance of the migration discourse within the meetings.

Thematic cluster	Migration	Development	Security	Humanitarian-development nexus	Humanitarian-development-peace nexus	Conflict
Number of times mentioned	219	53	6	4	2	2
Number of times mentioned per page	4	1	0.12	0.07	0.03	0.03

Table 3. Content analysis of the EUTF board meeting minutes.

Figure 1 offers insights into the evolution of the rhetoric from 2015 to 2022, revealing a sustained emphasis on migration, significantly prevailing over development and security for the duration of the programme. These findings indicate that despite these three themes being officially articulated as core objectives of the programme, the board's discussions predominantly centred on addressing migration issues. While the official rhetoric emphasises the EUTF's endeavour to simultaneously foster stability and tackle the root causes of migration and displacement, describing those as 'twin goals', the discussions reveal migration is the top priority (EU Commission, 2019, p.9).

Figure 1. Content Analysis of the EUTF board meeting minutes from 2015 to 2022, coding for three thematic clusters: migration, development, and security.

While discussions on development fluctuated between 2017 and 2020, they remained far below migration-related issues in all instances. These mentions mostly occurred during debates between different EU Member States, questioning whether the EUTF should address development given its short-term nature or whether this should be delegated to other EU instruments (EU Commission, 2018, p. 3).

A close inspection of the 2021 Annual Report indicates that the decline in discussions surrounding migration issues in 2020 can be attributed to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic rather than indicating a sustained shift in rhetoric (EU Commission, 2021, p. 10). Indeed, the pandemic heavily disrupted the EUTF's operations and halted migration flows from Africa. This is evidenced by the subsequent resurgence in migration-related discourse in 2021.

Figure 2. Content Analysis of the EUTF board meeting minutes from 2015 to 2022, coding for six thematic clusters: migration, development, security, humanitarian-development nexus, humanitarian-development-peace nexus, and conflict.

As depicted in Figure 2, a subtle shift in rhetoric occurred in 2018, introducing two additional concerns into the discourse. From 2018 to 2019, the humanitarian-development nexus started to appear in the EUTF rhetoric. It was replaced by the humanitarian-development-peace nexus in 2020, followed by a return to the humanitarian-development nexus in 2022. This evolution in rhetoric suggests a departure from the sole focus on migration issues towards a more comprehensive approach centred around a human rights-led approach to development and peacebuilding. However, when taking a closer look at the board meeting minutes, these two nexuses were primarily championed by one actor, rather than being incorporated into the wider rhetoric of the board. From 2018, the Director General for DG ECHO consistently raised these concerns, with only one instance of mention by another stakeholder, Spain, in 2019 (EU Commission, 2019, p. 4). This disparity highlights that these two nexuses were largely overlooked by other stakeholders. The EUTF's rhetoric thus did not shift towards prioritising these nexuses and remained focused on migration issues.

This sub-section demonstrates that despite development and security being theoretically the core goals of the EUTF, they consistently took a backseat to migration issues in board discussions. This imbalance, with migration dominating discussion, indicates a shift towards aid securitisation within the EUTF's internal rhetoric.

B. Annual Reports

It is crucial to juxtapose the rhetoric derived from the EUTF board meetings with the outcomes reflected in the Annual Reports published by the EU Commission, as these reflect the official narrative of the EUTF. This comparison provides a comprehensive understanding of the EUTF discourse and whether its rhetoric shifted towards aid securitisation.

Table 4. presents the results of the content analysis. Of the 278 pages coded, migration-related terms were mentioned 835 times, compared to 218 for security and 165 for development. This disparity underscores a persistent trend towards prioritising migration concerns, alongside an increasing emphasis on security in the official EUTF rhetoric, despite claims of adopting a balanced approach across all three goals (EU Commission, 2019, p. 6).

Thematic cluster	Migration	Development	Security	Humanitarian -development nexus	Humanitarian -development-peace nexus	Conflict
Number of times mentioned	835	165	218	6	7	158
Number of times mentioned per page	3	0.59	0.78	0.02	0.02	0.56

Table 4. Content analysis of the EUTF Annual Reports.

Upon examining the first three thematic clusters analysed—migration, development, and security—it becomes evident that the rhetoric differs from what was observed in the board meeting minutes. Mentions of migration still persistently outweighed mentions of development or security in both types of documents, indicating a consistent emphasis on migration-related issues. However, while security was notably absent from board meetings after 2018, it gained prominence in the Annual Reports and surpassed mentions of development for all years, despite a drop in 2018 as Figure 3 illustrates.

Figure 3. Content analysis of the EUTF Annual Reports from 2016 to 2022, coding for three thematic clusters: migration, development, and security.

Indeed, the Annual Reports underscore the EU's growing concerns with security and conflict prevention, contrasting with its sporadic mention in internal discussions. A close inspection of the reports outlines the emphasis on security; security and migration are described as 'twin goals', replacing the same description tying migration and development together (EU Commission, 2017, p.5). This outlines a sustained shift towards aid securitisation, with prominence given to migration and security, and development lagging.

Figure 4. Content Analysis of the EUTF Annual Reports from 2016 to 2022, coding for six thematic clusters: migration, development, security, humanitarian-development nexus, humanitarian-development-peace nexus, and conflict.

Moreover, 2017 marked a significant milestone with the introduction of the first nexus, the humanitarian-development nexus, approved by the Council in its 2017 general conclusions (EU Commission, 2017, p. 4). The 2017 Annual Report describes the EU as playing a pivotal role in its operationalisation (EU Commission, 2017, p. 4). While this nexus was sporadically mentioned by DG ECHO in board meetings, it emerged as a central concept in the 2017 Annual Report, being mentioned six times. While it evolved into the humanitarian-development-peace nexus in 2019, mentions of these nexuses decreased over time, eventually disappearing from the reports by 2022. This shows this approach was mainly used as a framing device to cover up for the intrinsic goals of the EUTF and address experts' concerns about aid securitisation, which emerged starting in 2017.

This subsection reveals that despite the EUTF's emphasis on a development-led approach to migration, a comprehensive analysis of the Annual Reports reveals a notable neglect of the developmental aspect, with security and migration issues taking precedence (EU Commission, 2016, p. 4).

This chapter evaluated both the board meeting minutes and Annual Reports to provide insights into the EUTF's rhetoric: examining internal strategic deliberations among board members and the resultant official discourse. This comparative analysis highlighted a discernible shift in EUTF rhetoric towards aid securitisation. It outlined the programme's evolving focus towards migration issues, with security gaining traction over time. Whether this subversion of developmental objectives represents merely a shift in rhetoric, or a substantive change in the substance of the programme warrants further examination, as will be explored in the following chapter.

CHAPTER 3: AID SECURITISATION IN THE SUBSTANCE OF THE EUTF

After uncovering a shift towards aid securitisation in the discourse of the EUTF, this chapter will assess whether such a shift is also reflected in the substance of the programme. It will first analyse its strategic objectives (SO), the funding allocated to each SO, and the EUTF's impacts on development cooperation for the future of EU programmes through a thorough review of the mid-term, lessons learned, board meeting minutes and Annual Reports of the EUTF.

A. Strategic Objectives

At its inception in 2015, the EUTF centred its actions around the four strategic objectives (SO) presented in Table 5.

Strategic objective EUTF (EU Commission, 2016, p. 8)	Valletta Action Plan pillars (Valletta Summit, 2015, pp. 2-17).
SO 1: Greater economic and employment opportunities	Pillar 1: Development benefits of migration
SO 2: Strengthening resilience of communities	Pillar 2: Legal migration
SO 3: Improved migration management	Pillar 3: Asylum
SO 4: Improved governance and conflict prevention and reduction of irregular migration	Pillar 4: Fight against irregular migration
	Pillar 5: Return and readmission

Table 5. The EUTF Strategic Objectives and Valletta Action Plan pillars.

At first glance, SO₃, aimed at improving migration management, seems to be the only strategic objective purely focusing on migration issues, with SO₄ overlapping when funding border management and state-building capacity projects to cope with increased migration flows (EU Commission, 2020, p. 5). The first two objectives seem to tackle developmental issues, suggesting that the EUTF is not a case of aid securitisation. However, it is imperative to consider the close association between the EUTF and the Valletta Action Plan. The EUTF was established during the Valletta Summit in 2015 and, therefore, acts within the framework of the Valletta Action Plan, a set of five different objectives that migration cooperation programmes should further, as outlined in Table 5. The 2016 Annual Report highlights that the programme should be guided by the Valletta principles while finding a balance among the five pillars (EU Commission, 2016, p. 5). When taking a closer look, SO₁ and SO₂, while focusing on development, are mainly targeted to the needs of migrants, and not the population of receiving states (EU Commission, 2020, p.36). This highlights the centrality of migration issues and the Valletta Action Plan in the EUTF's projects and actions, showing it takes precedence over the EUTF's portrayed aims of addressing developmental issues. Indeed, the board meeting minutes only refer to the EUTF's objectives in reference to the pillars of the VAP, showing its centrality despite the EUTF having its own strategic objectives. The strategic objectives appear to serve as smokescreens to hide the underlying objectives of the EUTF, which further the Valletta Action Plan.

This shift became more explicit in the 2017 board meeting, when the EEAS suggested that the programme should focus on pillars 2-5 of the VAP, and that pillar 1, which aims to enhance the development benefits of migration, should be addressed by other EU instruments (EU Commission, 2017, p. 4). Despite the title of the EUTF being purposefully aimed at solving development issues, its strategic objectives and priorities were derived solely to address migration issues. In 2017, funding was facing significant constraints, meaning objectives had to be reconsidered to select a lower number of areas of focus (EU Commission, 2017, p. 4). As such, new priorities and objectives emerged: return and reintegration, refugee management, securitisation of civil documents, anti-trafficking, stabilisation efforts in the SLC region and enhancing migration dialogues with partner countries (EU Commission, 2018, p. 4). The scarcity of resources thus redirected the EUTF to solely address migration issues, and, to a lesser extent, stabilisation and security. These six new priorities adopted in 2017 remained unchanged throughout the duration of the programme, even in the face of additional funding.

In addition, the North of Africa (NOA) window, managed by the DG NEAR, operates with distinct objectives. NOA solely focuses on SO₃: migration management, through its four unique priorities ranging from reintegration to border management (EU Commission, 2021, p. 2). Indeed, NOA is the direct migratory route leading to the EU. As such, projects funded are directly related to deterring migration before it reaches the EU, through funding the Libyan coastguards, for example (EU Commission, 2018, p.1). This window, explicitly focused on migration objectives and overlooking developmental ones, constitutes a case of aid securitisation.

B. Funding by Strategic Objectives

This subsection examines whether the EUTF shifted towards aid securitisation in allocating more funding to objectives that advanced its migration agenda.

The EUTF Annual Reports provide information on the amounts approved by strategic objectives for the different windows. Figure 5 illustrates the amount allocated to different objectives and regional windows at the end of the programme in 2022.

Figure 5. Amount approved by strategic objective and window as of 2022 (EUTF, 2022, p. 18).

While SO₃, focused on migration management, was allocated the largest amount (1,515.7M EUR), it comes close to SO₂, one of the SO aimed at development issues (1,384.6M EUR). This suggests that migration is given roughly the same investments as objectives addressing development issues. However, upon closer examination of what kind of projects fit in the different objectives, it becomes apparent that each SO contributes in some manner to addressing migration and aligns with SO₃. Indeed, SO₁ encompasses projects aimed at decreasing the dependency of the local population on income generated from migration flows, while SO₄ entails initiatives such as police forces training on border control (EU Commission, 2020, pp. 24-27). Although these projects are not officially categorised under SO₃, they undeniably target migration issues. Figure 6, retrieved from the 2021 *Learning Lessons from the EUTF* report, illustrates this redirection of SO towards fulfilling SO₃. This report, conducted by an independent consulting firm, highlights this discrepancy with official statistics and narratives.

6. Perimeter of migration, mobility and forced displacement-related activities across the four strategic objectives of the EUTF (EU Commission, 2021, p. 6).

When considering this overlap with SO₃, 51% of the EUTF funding has gone to migration-related projects, compared to the 31% announced in the official reports (EU Commission, 2021, p. 5). Overall, only about a

third of the funding has been spent towards projects furthering developmental and governance objectives (Youngs and Zihnioglu, 2021, p. 131). Moreover, as of 2020, 60% of the funding provided by EU Member States came from two major destination countries: Italy and Germany. This shows the EUTF was diverted to fulfil Member States' interests towards addressing migration issues rather than development.

C- Impact On Future Development Cooperation Programmes

As this analysis and the early EUTF literature outline, the EUTF presents the first case of mainstreaming migration into development cooperation, offering insights into the trajectory of EU aid programmes after the Valletta Summit (Chadwick, 2017; Pacciardi, 2024, p. 1). As indicated by the EU Commission (2016, p. 4), the EUTF serves as a pilot programme inspiring future programmes. Indeed, the EU acted as both a development and migration global actor for the first time, entangling both issues in the future of EU programmes (Welfens and Bonjour, 2023, p. 954). Though both were meant to be addressed equally, an analysis of the mid-term review shows the EUTF became narrowly focused on border control, displacement, and irregular migration, even failing to mention development in its evaluation of the fund's outcomes (EU Commission, 2020, p. 67). The report also noted the EUTF's modest contributions in terms of development (EU Commission, 2020, p. 2).

While the EUTF has not reached its goal of reducing instability, forced displacement and irregular migration, it contributed to providing growing resources and awareness to these issues (EU Commission, 2020, p. 8). As the fourth recommendation of the midterm review outlined, the EUTF enabled the EU and its Member States to create a strong dialogue with partner countries, which future EU programmes will aim to build upon (EU Commission, 2020, pp. 2-10). Indeed, in 2021, the EU created a new instrument: the NDICI, with a first budget of 90 billion euros, 10% of it being allocated to migration and forced displacement, acknowledging the programme is guided by the experience of the EUTF (EU Commission, 2020, pp. 82-83). While the aim of this article is not to examine future EU development programmes and the wider implications the EUTF had on those, it still denotes a sustained shift towards migration issues, informed by the EUTF as a pilot programme (EU Commission, 2021, p. 3).

In summary, this chapter has shown that the substance of the EUTF has shifted towards aid securitisation. More than the majority of the programme's funding went towards migration management-related projects, and a close examination of its strategic objectives showed that they all aligned with the EU's migration management agenda. This prioritisation of migration issues over the EUTF's developmental initiatives indicates a sustained shift towards aid securitisation, which seems to be drawn upon in future EU projects.

CONCLUSION

Drawing on the definition of aid securitisation by Olivie and Pérez (2021, p. 1903), this work argued that both the rhetoric and substance of the EUTF have shifted towards aid securitisation. It reviewed the programme from its inception in 2015 to 2022, through publicly available documents published by the EU Commission, primarily board meeting minutes and the EUTF Annual Reports. 2017 marked a turning point as aid securitisation intensified through a change in the EUTF strategic trajectory, embracing six new priorities focused on migration management. Indeed, the scarce resources pushed the board to embrace a turn advocated by some Member States and DG HOME and DG NEAR since its inception. These actors have succeeded in pushing migration issues to the top of the agenda in board meetings, and following 2017, in Annual Reports and strategic objectives, reorienting the EUTF away from its initial developmental goals.

Chapter 1 analysed these internal divisions through the board meeting minutes. Chapter 2 delved into the EUTF's official and internal rhetoric through a content analysis of the board meeting minutes and Annual Reports. This research outlined a discernible shift towards aid securitisation in the EUTF rhetoric, with migration issues and securitisation gaining traction over time and development being almost absent. While the Annual Reports describe migration issues and development as twin goals, the former subverted the latter. Chapter 3 offered insights into the EUTF's substance, analysing its strategic objectives, funding allocated to each, and its implications on future development cooperation programmes. Indeed, the substance of the EUTF has also shifted towards aid securitisation, with its strategic objectives closely linked to the Valletta Action Plan, which primarily aims to reduce migration flows. This shift became more significant in 2017 when the EUTF committed to six new priorities, all related to migration. Moreover, more than half of the funding went towards migration management-related projects. In its evaluation, the

EUTF claims to have successfully placed migration cooperation on the international stage, which will be built upon by future EU aid programmes.

This article addressed the following research question: Has i) the rhetoric and ii) substance of the European Union Emergency Trust Fund for Africa (EUTF) shifted towards aid securitisation? The paper uncovered that both the substance and rhetoric of the EUTF shifted towards aid securitisation, migration, security, and stability issues, crowding out its developmental goals, with an intensification after 2017. The work here contributes to existing literature by researching the EUTF and its outcomes after its contracting period has ended. Indeed, only Pacciardi (2024) provided a recent review of the programme, while the rest of the literature focused on debates at the programme's inception in 2016 and 2017. While the early literature anticipated that the EUTF shifted towards aid securitisation, it failed to examine these claims over the running of the programme. Moreover, the literature focused on the fund's substance, overlooking the importance of analysing its rhetoric. My contribution offers an overview of the EUTF's shift towards aid securitisation, in both its rhetoric and substance, from its inception in 2015 to 2022, highlighting that the entirety of the programme constitutes a case of aid securitisation, with an intensification after 2017. The paper thus updates the debate around the EUTF's shift towards aid securitisation by offering a comprehensive review of both its rhetoric and substance through a content analysis of the EUTF board meeting minutes and Annual Reports. Should the conclusions of this work prove relevant to other EU development programmes, it would raise significant concerns about the potential deviation of EU policies from their original objectives, thereby jeopardising the intended purpose of Official Development Assistance. Additionally, this would have substantial implications for the economic development of recipient countries.

While this article offered a comprehensive overview of the EUTF by analysing both its rhetoric and substance, I acknowledge some limitations. The analysis of the internal rhetoric was limited to a study of the board meeting minutes, being the only publicly available documents offering insights into the different delegations' agendas. Further studies would benefit from gaining access to EU policymakers in the different directorates as well as interviewing official delegates representing several EU Member States. Due to time constraints and the inaccessibility of such actors to undergraduate students, this methodology was impossible to use. Moreover, this article delved into the macro level of the EUTF, looking at its wide objectives rather than analysing case studies of different projects. Future research could further explore the findings of this paper by looking at the possible divergence between the different geographical windows of the fund.

Lisa Lefebvre-Risso

REFERENCES

- Castillejo, C. (2016) "The European Trust Fund for Africa: a glimpse of the future for EU development cooperation," German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS), 22(1), pp.1-38.
- Castillejo, C. (2017) "The European Union Trust Fund for Africa: what implications for future EU development policy?," Deutsches Institut für Entwicklungspolitik (DIE), 5(1), pp.1-5.
- Chadwick, V. (2017) "What does EU development policy mean by "root causes of migration"?", Devex. Available at: <https://www.devex.com/news/what-does-eu-development-policy-mean-by-root-causes-of-migration-91369>. (Accessed 11th April 2024).
- Clemens, M.A. and Postel, H.M. (2018) "Deterring Emigration with Foreign Aid: An Overview of Evidence from Low-Income Countries," Population and Development Review, 44(4), pp.661-872.
- Council of the European Union (2003) European Security Strategy: A Secure Europe in a Better World. Available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/30823/qc7809568enc.pdf> (Accessed 11th April 2024).
- European Commission (no date) Emergency Trust Fund for Africa. Available at https://trust-fund-for-africa.europa.eu/index_en (Accessed 10th April 2024).
- European Commission (2015) "Board Meeting Minutes 12/11/2015, Hotel Dolmen, Valletta," EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa.
- European Commission (2016) "Minutes of the Second Board Meeting of the EUTF for Africa, Brussels, 13 December 2016," EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa.
- European Commission (2016) "2016 Annual Report," EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa.
- European Commission (2017) "Minutes of the Third Board Meeting of the EUTF for Africa, Brussels, 30 June 2017," EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa.
- European Commission (2017) "2017 Annual Report," EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa.
- European Commission (2018) "Minutes of the Fourth Board Meeting of the EUTF for Africa, Brussels, 24 April 2018," EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa.
- European Commission (2018) "Compte Rendu de la Cinquième Réunion du FFUE, Bruxelles, 21 Septembre 2018," EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa.

- European Commission (2018) "2018 Annual Report," EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa.
- European Commission (2019) "Sixth Board Meeting of the EUTF for Africa, Brussels, 14 June 2019," EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa.
- European Commission (2019) "2019 Annual Report," EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa.
- European Commission (2020) "Seventh Board Meeting of the EUTF for Africa, 29 September 2020," EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa.
- European Commission (2020) "2020 Rapport Annuel," Fonds Fiduciaire d'Urgence de l'UE pour l'Afrique.
- European Commission (2020) "Mid-term Evaluation of the European Union Emergency Trust Fund for stability and addressing root causes of irregular migration and displaced persons in Africa 2015-2019," EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa.
- European Commission (2021) "Eight Board Meeting of the EUTF for Africa, 7 December 2021," EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa.
- European Commission (2021) "2021 Annual Report," EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa.
- European Commission (2021) "Learning Lessons from the EUTF - Phase 2 - Paving the way for future programming on migration, mobility and forced displacement," EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa.
- European Commission (2022) "Ninth Board Meeting of the EUTF for Africa, 30 November 2022," EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa.
- European Commission (2022) "2022 Annual Report," EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa.
- European Court of Auditors (2018) "European Union Emergency Trust Fund for Africa: Flexible but lacking focus," 32(1), pp.1-51.
- European Council (2001) "Council directive 2001/40/EC on the mutual recognition of decisions on the expulsion of third country nationals (2001)," Official Journal, L49/34.
- European Parliament. (2016) Report on the EU Trust Fund for Africa: The implications for development and humanitarian aid (2015/2341(INI)). Strasbourg: Author, Committee on Development.
- Fakhoury, T. (2016) "Securitising Migration: The European Union in the Context of the Post2011 Arab Upheavals," *The International Spectator*, 51(4), pp.67-79.
- Furness, M. and Gänzle, S. (2017) "The Security-Development Nexus in European Union Foreign Relations after Lisbon: Policy Coherence at Last?," *Development Policy Review*, 35(4), pp.475-492.
- Hauck, V., Knoll, A. and Cangas, A.H. (2015) "EU Trust Funds - shaping more comprehensive external action?," Briefing note European Centre for Development Policy Management, 8(1), pp.1-17.
- Hoeffler, A. and Outram, V. (2011) "Need, Merit, or Self-Interest: What Determines the Allocation of Aid?," *Review of Development Economics*, 15(2), pp.237-250.
- Keukeleire, S., and Raube, K. (2013) "The Security-Development Nexus and Securitization in the EU's Policies towards Developing Countries" *Cambridge Review of International Affairs*, 26(3), pp.556-517.
- Kiratli, O.S. (2021) "Politicisation of Aiding Others: The Impact of Migration on European Public Opinion of Development Aid," *Journal of Common Market Studies*, 59(1), pp.53-71.
- Langan, M. and Price, S. (2021) "Migration, Development and EU Free Trade Deals: The Paradox of Economic Partnership Agreements as a Push Factor for Migration," *Global Affairs*, 7(4), pp. 505-521.
- Lauwers, N. et al. (2021) "The Politicisation of the Migration-Development Nexus: Parliamentary Discourse on the European Union Trust Fund on Migration," *Journal of Common Market Studies*, 59(1), pp.72-90.
- Lavenex, S. and Kunz, R. (2008) "The Migration-development nexus in EU external relations," *Journal of European integration*, 30(3), pp.439-457.
- Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) (no date) "Official development assistance - definition and coverage." Available at: <https://www.oecd.org/dac/financing-sustainable-development/development-finance-standards/officialdevelopmentassistancedefinitionandcoverage.htm> (Accessed 11th April 2024).
- Oliví, I. and Pérez, A. (2019) "Solidarity and Security in the EU Discourse on Aid," *Aid Power and Politics*, pp. 179-196. Oxford: Routledge.
- Oliví, I. and Pérez, A. (2021) "Whose and what aid securitisation? An analysis of EU aid narratives and flows," *Third World Quarterly*, 42(8), pp.1903-1922.
- Oxfam (2017) "An Emergency for Whom?: The EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa - migratory routes and development aid in Africa," Oxfam Briefing Notes. Available at: https://oifiles-d8-prod.s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/s3fs-public/file_attachments/bp-emergency-forwhom-eutf-africa-migration-151117-en_1.pdf. (Accessed 11th April 2024).
- Pacciardi, A. (2024) "A European narrative of border externalisation: the European Trust Fund for Africa Story," *European Security*, pp.1-20.
- United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) (2016) "2015: The year of Europe's refugee crisis." Available at [https://www.unhcr.org/uk/news/stories/2015-year-europes-refugee-crisis#:~:text=As%20of%20December%207%2C%20more,in%20Syria%2C%20Afghanistan%20or%20Iraq](https://www.unhcr.org/uk/news/stories/2015-year-europes-refugee-crisis#:~:text=As%20of%20December%207%2C%20more,in%20Syria%2C%20Afghanistan%20or%20Iraq.). (Accessed 11th April 2024).
- Welfens, N., and Bonjour, S. (2023) "Seeking Legitimacy Through Knowledge Production: The Politics of Monitoring and Evaluation of the EU Trust Fund for Africa," *Journal of Common Market Studies*, 61(1), pp.951-969.
- Youngs, R. and Zihniglo, O. (2021) "EU Aid Policy in the Middle East and North Africa: Politicization and its Limits," *Journal of Common Market Studies*, 59(1), pp.1-17.
- Zaun, N. and Nantermoz, O. (2023) "Depoliticising EU migration policies: the EUTF Africa and the politicisation of development aid," *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 49(12), pp.2986-3004.

APPENDIX

ACRONYM GLOSSARY

DG DEVCO: Directorate-General for International Cooperation and Development (until 2021)

DG ECHO: Directorate-General for European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations

DG HOME: Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs

DG INTPA: Directorate-General for International Partnerships (new name of DG DEVCO since 2021)

DG NEAR: Directorate-General for Neighbourhood and Enlargement Negotiations

EEAS: European External Action Service

EU: European Union

EUTF: European Union Emergency Trust Fund for Africa

HOA: Horn of Africa window

NOA: North of Africa window

ODA: Official Development Assistance

SLC: Sahel and Lake Chad window

VAP: Valletta Action Plan